

The effects of humidity on ester hydrolysis and oxidation in aging oil paint

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ABSTRACT

Water plays a critical role in the chemical processes that occur during aging of oil paint, but the detailed effects of environmental humidity on the interlinked reaction pathways of hydrolysis and oxidation are not well understood. We report the results of long-term artificial aging experiments on oil paints prepared with iron oxide, zinc white, vine black and unpigmented films. The films were frequently monitored with attenuated total reflection Fourier-transform infrared (ATR-FTIR) spectroscopy, after which concentration estimates for various carbonyl species could be extracted using a combination of curve fitting and calibration.

Using this thorough analysis approach, it was demonstrated that ester hydrolysis reaches an equilibrium state in iron oxide oil paint. In contrast, in zinc white oil paint the rapid formation of zinc carboxylates drives the ester hydrolysis process towards completion. The large dataset of ATR-FTIR spectra also revealed that the sensitivity of oil paint to humidity and the relative importance of hydrolysis and oxidation degradation pathways both depend strongly on pigmentation. These results shed light on the complex chemistry of oil paint aging, and are important to support decisions on indoor climate conditions for museums.

1. Introduction

Humidity influences the chemistry of an oil paint. Despite the relatively hydrophobic nature of aged oil paint binding media, humid environmental conditions are associated with elevated levels of carboxylic acids and other products, both in model paint systems [1–4] and painted artworks [5–8]. These water-driven chemical reactions can lead indirectly to visual [9] and mechanical damage [5,10] in model paints. In all likelihood, humidity has played a key role in the current chemistry of historical artworks, although often detailed information about past environmental conditions is lacking. Understanding the chemistry of change in oil paint and the role of humidity in those processes will lead to better support for decisions on collection care which includes environmental guidelines for the museum climate. Humidity is also one of the few factors in the museum climate that can be controlled to some degree.

In its simplest form, an oil paint consists of one or several pigments and an oil binder. Drying oils which are suitable for paintings, such as linseed oil, walnut oil or safflower oil, are composed of triglycerides with a high content of polyunsaturated fatty acids. Upon exposure to oxygen, these oils undergo free-radical polymerization to form a complex three-dimensional polymer network [11–15]. This process, also called autoxidation, includes a large number of possible

reactions. Some of them lead to the formation of various types of cross-links, oxygen-containing functional groups and small molecular fragments [16,17].

Polymerized oil is only weakly polar and absorbs rather little water, but it is still sensitive to humidity during aging. The maximum internal water concentration in an oil paint is typically not higher than 5 wt% at 90%RH (relative humidity) [18,19], depending on the age and pigmentation of the paint. The internal water concentration is even lower (< 2 wt%) at typical ambient RH in museums (40–60 %RH) [18]. The change in internal water concentration seems small between mid- and high humidity conditions for oil paints, but exposure to high humidity has been demonstrated to lead to elevated concentrations of (di)acids [1], (volatile) small molecules [16,17] and metal carboxylates [3,4,20] in model paints.

Many chemical reactions occur simultaneously in an aging oil paint. In theory, water absorbed in an oil paint can act as a solvent, a reactant or a catalyst for those reactions. As a solvent, water can swell the oil polymer network to some degree. This swelling can allow small molecules or ions to be solvated and travel more quickly or over longer length scales. Swelling can also increase the mobility of reactive polymer chain segments. As a reactant, water is perhaps most

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Fig. 1. A simplified reaction scheme for oil paint degradation. (I) Esters and water react to form carboxylic acids and an alcohols (hydrolysis) while a carboxylic acid and an alcohol can undergo the reversed reaction to form an ester and water (condensation). (II) A primary or secondary alcohol can oxidize to form an aldehyde or ketone, respectively. Ketones are stable and will not react further. Aldehydes can further oxidize into carboxylic acids. (III) A carboxylic acid can react with metal ions to form metal carboxylates. (IV) Other oxidative and radical pathways can form alcohols, aldehydes, ketones or carboxylic acids in a wide variety of reactions. As all these reactions take place, water can absorb or desorb with varying external humidity conditions, and small molecules can evaporate.

prominently active in the hydrolysis of ester bonds which persist as the oil polymerizes [12]. However, water may also be involved in the formation of oxidized functional groups like ketones, aldehydes and carboxylic acids, or in oxidative cleavage reactions [21]. Lastly, water is believed to catalyze several steps in the formation of various metal carboxylate species that form spontaneously in some common oil paints [22]. Hence, it is worth discussing the relationships between water and oil reactivity in some more detail. Fig. 1 illustrates the key reaction processes in oil paint related to water.

Focusing first on ester hydrolysis (Fig. 1, part I), this reaction usually establishes an equilibrium with ester condensation. Under most reaction conditions, ester formation tends to be the more favorable process. In an oil paint, where water concentrations are relatively low, one might expect only a limited extent of ester hydrolysis. In addition, one may wonder whether a global equilibrium will ever be established in a polymer network matrix where reactant diffusion is rather limited. However, several factors may drive ester hydrolysis forward. For instance, some of the smaller alcohols and carboxylic acids can evaporate. Secondly, some pigments (especially those containing lead or zinc) are known to react easily and irreversibly with carboxylic acid groups to form metal carboxylates (Fig. 1, part III), which could make hydrolysis into a one-way reaction. Finally, on-going generation of polar functional groups through hydrolysis and oxidation may increase the sorption of water from the environment, effectively creating a positive feedback loop, although this effect has not yet been proven and requires more in-depth study [23].

Oxidation reactions (Fig. 1, part II) are the second class of reactions that have a large influence on the properties of aged oil paint. Oxidative cleavage reactions occur during paint drying, but can also remain relevant for long-term oil paint degradation. After drying, a significant concentration of reactive $-C=C-$ bonds was proven to be present in cured model paints [12]. In the months or years after applying a paint, there is also a steady release of volatile compounds, indicating the formation of small fragments through cleavage reactions [17]. Alcohols formed by oxidative cleavage or other reactions may oxidize further to form aldehydes, ketones and carboxylic acids.

The drying and aging reactions of oil paints have been the topic of numerous studies. These studies consistently found that (1) a higher humidity promoted the formation of oxidation and hydrolysis products during aging [1,24], (2) that the aging reactions in oil paints were greatly influenced by the type of pigment [24–27], (3) the drying

and curing reactions of oil paints were significantly affected by its surroundings [12] and internal composition [12,28–33] and (4) metal carboxylate formation is affected by humidity and type of pigment [2, 3,20]. However, most studies on water-induced chemical change often do not report on the internal water concentration of studied oil paints, which is an essential step towards a complete picture of the chemistry during oil paint aging. While the effect of very low and high humidity conditions have been evaluated in various studies [1,25,34], the effects of mid-range humidity levels closer to realistic indoor climates is less well charted. This information is very important to support environmental guidelines for collection care, as the chemical response to environmental humidity may well be non-linear.

Untangling the different reaction pathways during oil paint aging is particularly challenging. Many species can originate from different reactants, e.g. carboxylic acids are formed by both ester hydrolysis and the oxidation of aldehydes. Nevertheless, a distinction between pathways can be made by quantifying the formation and consumption of the reactants and products simultaneously. While quantification of functional group populations in curing oil paints is difficult, given the insoluble nature of cured paint and its often poorly reproducible curing process, this approach is crucial to map the reaction pathways of aging paint and the influence of humidity.

The aim of this study is to investigate how humidity conditions and pigment type influence the water-driven aging reactions in oil paint. Unpigmented linseed oil films (LO) were compared to paints prepared with red iron oxide (hematite), zinc oxide and vine black. Hematite particles are known to catalyze oxidation processes [35,36], while zinc oxide reacts easily with carboxylic acid groups to form zinc carboxylates [37]. In contrast, vine black is an organic pigment and delays auto-oxidation during drying [38]. For that reason, the resulting polymer network can be less cross-linked and may age differently than mineral-containing oil paints [1,1,24–26]. Attenuated total reflection Fourier-transform infrared (ATR-FTIR) spectroscopy was used to quantify the concentrations of esters and other carbonyl-containing species in oil paints during aging at 11, 28, 50 and 75%RH to determine the relative impact of oxidation and ester hydrolysis at those humidity levels. The internal water concentrations of the studied oil paints were also characterized using dynamic vapor sorption (DVS) measurements. The combination of exposing the paint films to four different humidity levels, using different pigment types, and detailed quantitative spectral analysis sheds light on the relative impact of oxidation, ester hydrolysis and metal carboxylate formation during aging and contributes to a better understanding of an oil paint's chemical response to humidity.

2. Materials and methods

2.1. Paint film preparation

Model oil paints were prepared by mixing pigment and linseed oil (Kremer Pigmente, product number 73020) using a mortar and pestle. The paint films were applied on a glass slide using a draw-down bar with a spacing of 90 μm . The samples were cured in an oven at 60 $^{\circ}\text{C}$ for one week. Paint films pigmented with vine black and red iron oxide (hematite, Fe_2O_3 , Kremer Pigmente) were prepared with 50 wt% pigment, later referred to as B50 and R50, respectively. Zinc white (ZnO , Sigma Aldrich, < 100 nm particle size) paint films were prepared with 67 wt% pigment (W67). The composition and purity of the pigments were confirmed using powder X-ray diffraction (Supporting Information, Section D). In addition, unpigmented linseed oil (LOP) films were prepared in a similar fashion, as well as red iron oxide paint films with pigment concentrations ranging from 10 to 60 wt% hematite.

2.2. Oil paint aging

The paint films were aged at 70 $^{\circ}\text{C}$ in four different humidity environments after curing. These environments were created using 1.8 liter glass boxes (IKEA, catalogue number: 292.690.74) and saturated salt solutions: lithium chloride (LiCl , 11 RH%), magnesium chloride (MgCl_2 , 28 RH%), sodium bromide (NaBr , 50 RH%), and sodium chloride (NaCl , 75 RH%) [39]. The saturated salt solutions were prepared in a beaker using demineralized water with an excess amount of salt.

2.3. ATR-FTIR spectroscopy

ATR-FTIR spectra were collected on a Frontier spectrometer (PerkinElmer) equipped with a diamond GladiATR module (Pike Technologies). In general, the individual spectra were collected with a resolution of 4 cm^{-1} and 8 scans. In the first two weeks of aging, an average of two or four scans was collected. At each time point, at least two measurements on distinct fragments were carried out for every paint film. Data was collected on the top paint surface in most cases. However, at long aging times R50 and B50 films became too soft and the paint was smeared out on the ATR crystal instead. No major differences were observed between spectra collected on either side of these paint films. All spectra were processed and analyzed using custom Python scripts. A linear baseline between 1480 and 1820 cm^{-1} was subtracted from all spectra and they were normalized to the CH_2 bending vibration at 1456 cm^{-1} , after which duplicate spectra were averaged.

2.4. Dynamic vapor sorption

DVS analysis was performed on paint films with a thickness of roughly 60 μm with masses ranging between 20 and 130 mg using an automatic multisample moisture sorption analyzer (SPSx-11 m, Projekt Messtechnik). The relative humidity was controlled by mixing a dry nitrogen gas flow with an air gas flow saturated with water. The mass of the samples was measured every ten minutes with a microbalance (WXS2026SDU, Mettler Toledo) and the temperature was kept constant at 22 $^{\circ}\text{C}$. Before the measurements, the samples were dried at 0%RH for 300 h. The RH was increased stepwise every 50 h with 10%RH until 90%RH was reached, with a final %RH step from 90 to 95%RH. An equilibrium moisture sorption concentration (EMC) was reached when the mass change was smaller than 0.001 mg over a period of 60 min. Moisture sorption isotherms were calculated as $m_{\text{water}}/V_{\text{LO}}$ by taking into account the mass fractions of pigments in the oil and material density estimates, to allow a direct comparison of water concentrations in the polymerized binding media between various pigmented and unpigmented films.

3. Results

3.1. Quantification of carbonyl concentrations with ATR-FTIR spectroscopy

In order to study the molecular changes in oil paint during humidity exposure, we developed a method to estimate the concentrations of carbonyl groups using a calibration series and IR band fitting. A calibration curve was constructed by measuring ATR-FTIR spectra of mixtures with varying ratios of a carboxylic acid (octanoic acid) and an ester (ethyl linoleate). The carbonyl bands of that liquid mixture were described exceptionally well by Lorentzian band shapes, though Gaussian band shapes proved to be a better fit for the carbonyl bands in polymerized linseed oil. The quantification procedure is described in detail in Supporting Information Section C, but the method is described briefly here.

Calibration curves were constructed using the fitted Lorentzian band shapes (Fig. 2). The infrared spectra were normalized at 1456 cm^{-1} and the normalized area under the curve was determined for each Lorentzian band. The calculated areas, with respect to the concentration of CH_2 groups, was plotted against the corresponding molar concentration of ethyl linoleate or octanoic acid (Fig. 2b). The calibration series were fitted with a linear curve and showed a near-linear relationship in most of the concentration range. Since the slopes for the ester and carboxylic acid species were very similar, we assumed that all considered carbonyl species have approximately the same extinction coefficient. The linear relationship was used to determine the concentration of esters, carboxylic acids and other carbonyl species.

The carbonyl region in aging oil paint samples was modeled using a constrained fit with six Gaussian band shapes. Ideally, one would model each contribution to the carbonyl band envelope explicitly with known information about the number of bands, their positions and shapes. However, the close overlap of several bands and their tendency to shift position and change width to some degree over the course of an aging experiment makes it impossible to obtain reliable fits where each contribution can be assigned to a unique functional group [12]. Due to this complexity, we chose to group the $\nu(\text{C}=\text{O})_{\text{carboxylic acid}}$, $\nu(\text{C}=\text{O})_{\text{aldehyde}}$ and $\nu(\text{C}=\text{O})_{\text{ketone}}$ contributions into a single broad band (hereafter referred to as $\nu(\text{C}=\text{O})_{\text{CAK}}$), made possible by their significant spectral overlap. The total CAK concentration was determined using the extinction coefficient of octanoic acid, and the assumption of a fixed internal concentration of CH_2 groups (38.4 M) in the oil binder, based on the fatty acid distribution of linseed oil determined previously [12].

The contributions were assigned as follows: $\nu(\text{C}=\text{O})_{\text{CAK}}$ (1710 cm^{-1}), $\nu(\text{C}=\text{O})_{\text{ester}}$ (1738 cm^{-1}) and a contribution of secondary oxidation products $\nu(\text{C}=\text{O})_{\text{sec. ox. products}}$ centered at 1760 cm^{-1} . A broad absorption tail was also identified between 1500–1650 cm^{-1} . This tail was pragmatically modeled using three additional Gaussian band shapes, but since it can contain non-carbonyl vibrations, e.g. the bending mode of water, no particular chemical meaning was attributed to this part of the spectra.

3.2. Aging of polymerized linseed oil under low and high humidity

The effects of humidity on ester hydrolysis and oxidation processes was investigated qualitatively first by exposing unpigmented linseed oil (LOP) to low (11%RH) and high humidity (75%RH) at 70 $^{\circ}\text{C}$ for 83 days. The chemical changes during aging were characterized with ATR-FTIR spectroscopy (Figs. 3, S1 and S2). Changes in carboxylic acid, aldehyde, ketone, alcohol and ester concentration were monitored using the intense carbonyl stretch bands around 1720 cm^{-1} , the carboxylic stretch bands at approximately 2500 cm^{-1} , the broad O–H stretch bands near 3400 cm^{-1} and the contributions of C–O stretch vibrations in the region between 1000 and 1300 cm^{-1} .

The intense band in the carbonyl region contains overlapping contributions from esters ($\nu(\text{C}=\text{O})_{\text{ester}}$, 1744 cm^{-1}), carboxylic acids ($\nu(\text{C}=\text{O})_{\text{carboxylic acid}}$, 1710 cm^{-1}), aldehydes ($\nu(\text{C}=\text{O})_{\text{aldehyde}}$,

Fig. 2. (a) An example of an ATR-FTIR spectrum for a 70/30 volume ratio of octanoic acid and ethyl linoleate, modeled with two Lorentzian curves. (b) The calculated band areas vs. molar concentration of octanoic acid and ethyl linoleate, showing approximately linear relationships. The spectra were baselined between 1500–1820 cm^{-1} and normalized at 1456 cm^{-1} .

Fig. 3. ATR-FTIR spectra of the carbonyl region (1500–1900 cm^{-1}) in LOP during 83 days of aging at 70 °C at (a) 11%RH and (b) 75%RH. The mean of ATR-FTIR spectra in the carbonyl region at each unique time point is shown after baseline correction (1480–1820 cm^{-1}) and normalization at 1456 cm^{-1} .

1718 cm^{-1}) and ketones ($\nu(\text{C}=\text{O})_{\text{ketone}}$, 1725 cm^{-1}). The exact position of each contribution can vary depending on its molecular environment, such as the extent of intermolecular hydrogen bonding. Each of these species is involved in oxidation and hydrolysis reactions during oil paint aging as highlighted in Fig. 1 (Parts I and II).

While there was only minimal change in the carbonyl region during aging at 11%RH, clear signs of oxidation and hydrolysis were observed during aging of LOP at 75%RH (Fig. 3b). The spectra show a decrease of $\nu(\text{C}=\text{O})_{\text{ester}}$ and an increasing intensity of overlapping $\nu(\text{C}=\text{O})_{\text{carboxylic acid}}$, $\nu(\text{C}=\text{O})_{\text{aldehyde}}$ and $\nu(\text{C}=\text{O})_{\text{ketone}}$ bands. A new band maximum appeared at 1706 cm^{-1} , which is close to the typical band position of carboxylic acids. This can be a sign that the carboxylic acids became most dominant carbonyl species. The increased abundance of carboxylic acid groups was further illustrated by the $\nu(\text{C}-\text{O})$ band around 1418 cm^{-1} (Figure S1c) and a band at 2500 cm^{-1} (Figure S1d). The $\nu(\text{C}-\text{O})$ peak position shifted to lower wavenumbers and also increased in intensity. In addition, the band at 2500 cm^{-1} increased in intensity during aging. The fact that there was virtually no change in the shape of the carbonyl band at 11 RH% and other regions of the spectra despite the high aging temperature suggests that also the oxidation pathways towards new carbonyl species depend on water.

Looking beyond the carbonyl vibrations, the O–H stretch band ($\nu(\text{O}-\text{H})$, 3393 cm^{-1}) increased in intensity (Figure S1d) and the band shifted

towards lower wavenumbers. These changes are difficult to interpret in detail, because the increased intensity could stem from the formation of alcohols and/or carboxylic acids, and/or an increase in the equilibrium moisture concentration in the oil due to increased polarity. The band shift is likely due to more extensive intermolecular hydrogen bonding, which may be a sign of this increased polarity. Reliably isolating the individual contributions of the various O–H species was not possible with the current set of ATR-FTIR spectra given the high degree of band overlap and variations in band widths and position.

The observed spectral changes suggest that both hydrolysis and oxidation processes contributed to the formation of carboxylic acids and other functional groups at 75%RH. In the carbonyl region, there was no clear isosbestic point between the maxima of the ester and carboxylic acid bands, demonstrating that carboxylic acids formed also through pathways other than hydrolysis or that there was simultaneous formation of aldehydes and/or ketones. This hypothesis was further strengthened by the fact that the total band area in the carbonyl region increased with aging time.

3.3. Oxidation and ester hydrolysis in iron oxide oil paint

The scheme for water-driven oil paint reactivity showed that the ester hydrolysis equilibrium has a prominent role in oil paint degradation

Fig. 4. ATR-FTIR spectra of R60 aged at 70 °C and at (a) 11%RH and (b) 75%RH after aging at 75%RH for 35 days. (c) The concentration ratio between CAK species and esters during aging before and after a humidity change. Data points are shown for each collected spectrum without averaging.

(Fig. 1, Part I). However, it is not yet clear whether ester hydrolysis behaves as an equilibrium process in aging oil paint. To study the reversibility of ester hydrolysis in oil paint, iron oxide oil paint (R60, 60 wt%) was first aged at 75 RH% for 35 days and then either moved to 11%RH, 28%RH or kept at 11%RH, all at 70 °C. Fig. 4a and b show ATR-FTIR spectra collected at frequent intervals to monitor changes in the carbonyl region of these samples.

During initial aging at 75%RH, the contributions of $\nu(\text{C}=\text{O})_{\text{carboxylic acid}}$, $\nu(\text{C}=\text{O})_{\text{aldehyde}}$, and $\nu(\text{C}=\text{O})_{\text{ketone}}$ increased strongly relative to $\nu(\text{C}=\text{O})_{\text{ester}}$. After approximately twenty days, the system stabilized and spectral changes in the carbonyl region were minor. In contrast, we observed a clear relative increase in the $\nu(\text{C}=\text{O})_{\text{ester}}$ band after the paint film was transferred to a low humidity environment after 35 days (Fig. 4a). Using the method described in Section 3.1, a concentration estimate for $\nu(\text{C}=\text{O})_{\text{CAK}}$ and $\nu(\text{C}=\text{O})_{\text{ester}}$ in R60 was determined. In Fig. 4c, the resulting concentration ratios between $\nu(\text{C}=\text{O})_{\text{CAK}}$ and $\nu(\text{C}=\text{O})_{\text{ester}}$ are shown. The concentration profiles only showed minor fluctuations in the CAK/ester ratio after continued aging at 75%RH, while there was a significant drop in this ratio during aging at both 28 and 11%RH. While there was some variation in calculated concentration ratios between duplicate measurements, the observed decrease in CAK/ester ratio after transfer to a low humidity environment far exceeded those variations. These observations strongly suggest that, at least on a short timescale, ester hydrolysis in oil paint is reversible to some degree and a function of the internal water concentration, which in turn is determined by external humidity conditions. Therefore, we should consider the implications of ester hydrolysis as an equilibrium process in oil paint.

3.4. Effects of metal carboxylate formation on ester hydrolysis

Having demonstrated the reversibility of ester hydrolysis in iron oxide oil paint, it is of interest to investigate the effect of removing a reactant from the hydrolysis/condensation equilibrium (Fig. 1, Part III). For this purpose, a zinc white oil paint was studied during artificial

aging. This paint is known to form zinc carboxylates during aging [2, 3,20]. Hence, zinc white paint films (67 wt%, W67) were subjected to 75%RH for more than eight months and monitored by ATR-FTIR spectroscopy. For comparison, an iron oxide and vine black paint (R50 and B50) were aged under the same conditions.

The evolution of the carbonyl region of W67 during aging is rather different than the iron oxide oil paint (Fig. 5a and c). The $\nu(\text{C}=\text{O})_{\text{ester}}$ band remained the dominant contribution to the carbonyl region until 27 days, and the carbonyl region as a whole decreased dramatically until there was virtually no $\nu(\text{C}=\text{O})$ signal left after 255 days of aging. In contrast, R50 and B50 were stored under the same conditions and showed a significant carbonyl band after 255 days of aging, including the $\nu(\text{C}=\text{O})_{\text{ester}}$ contribution. In tandem with the decreasing intensity of the carbonyl region W67, zinc carboxylates were detected between 1500 and 1650 cm^{-1} (Fig. 5b). These zinc carboxylates were initially limited to non-crystalline oxo and chain complexes, while after 6 days characteristic bands of type A and B crystalline zinc soaps started to appear [20,40]. While a detailed characterization of zinc carboxylate structures is outside the scope of this study, these results clearly demonstrated that zinc oxide is very effective at reacting with carboxylic acids generated through hydrolysis and oxidation processes. These spectra also demonstrate that the concentration of ketones and aldehydes in these oil paints must be quite low. After ester hydrolysis and metal carboxylate formation, ketones and aldehydes would be the only species to remain, but virtually no carbonyl signal is observed in highly aged W67.

To determine whether the stark differences in ester concentration between W67 and R50 or V50 are caused by metal carboxylate coordination or differences in internal water concentration (as was shown in Fig. 4), the absolute internal water concentration of W67 was compared to R50 with dynamic vapor sorption as a function of aging time at 75%RH and 70 °C (Fig. 5d and e). All isotherms showed a nonlinear increase in moisture sorption at high humidities, suggesting ‘pooling’ of water molecules [41]. The aging series of W67 and R50 showed only minor changes in internal water concentration during aging. This

Fig. 5. ATR-FTIR spectra of W67 in the (a) carbonyl region ($1650\text{--}1800\text{ cm}^{-1}$) and (b) zinc carboxylate region ($1500\text{--}1650\text{ cm}^{-1}$) during aging at 75%RH. (c) The carbonyl region of B50, R50 and W67 after 255 days of aging at 75 RH%. In (a) and (b), the mean of ATR-FTIR spectra at each unique time point is shown after baseline correction ($1480\text{--}1820\text{ cm}^{-1}$) and normalization at 1456 cm^{-1} . In (b), a baseline was subtracted between 1480 and 1650 cm^{-1} . Moisture sorption isotherms of (d) W67 and (e) R50 as function of aging time at 75%RH. (f) Carbonyl region of R50 and W67 after 27 days of aging at 75%RH.

finding suggests that ongoing oxidation and hydrolysis of the oil binder did not substantially change the equilibrium moisture content (EMC) in those paints. The slightly increased EMC in W67 after 47 days of aging is probably due to the low mass of this particular sample compared to the rest of the series, which may have led to a higher level of equilibration (see Supporting Information, Figure S7). The other clear outlier was unaged R50. A duplicate measurement was carried out on a different unaged R50 paint in a second DVS run (not shown), which showed a similar deviation from the EMC measured in the R50 aging series. It is still unclear which chemical changes might cause this clear shift in moisture sorption in iron oxide paints in the first two weeks of aging. In order to compare the water concentrations in R50 and W67, we focus on an aging time of approximately 30 days, in the middle of the aging series. At this time, the ATR-FTIR spectra (Fig. 5f) show an intense carbonyl region dominated by carboxylic acids for R50, while a much weaker set of bands was observed for W67 with a

maximum attributed to $\nu(\text{C}=\text{O})_{\text{ester}}$, demonstrating that W67 was far more hydrolyzed. However, the DVS data at 33 days aging actually shows a higher water concentration at 70 %RH in R50 ($0.060\text{ mg/mL}_{\text{LO}}$ or 3.33 mM) compared to W67 ($0.042\text{ mg/mL}_{\text{LO}}$ or 2.33 mM). These measurements clearly show that it is the presence of zinc that drives the hydrolysis reaction forward through metal carboxylate formation and prevents the establishment of a steady state that maintains high concentrations of both esters and carboxylic acids.

3.5. Relative contributions of oxidation and ester hydrolysis to carboxylic acid group formation

The effect of humidity exposure on oxidation processes and ester hydrolysis in oil paint was studied further as a function of pigmentation. For this purpose, LOP, R50 and B50 were aged at four humidity levels (11, 28, 50 and 75%RH) and monitored with ATR-FTIR spectroscopy

Fig. 6. Changes in the concentrations of oxidation/hydrolysis products (CAK) and esters for (a) LOp, (b) R50, (c) B50 during aging at 70 °C and 11, 28, 50 and 75 RH%. (d) Absolute concentration changes as function of iron oxide concentration (10–60 wt%) during aging at 70 °C and 75 RH%. Curves are merely guides to the eye.

(see Supporting Information Section A for spectra). The $\nu(\text{C}=\text{O})_{\text{ester}}$ and $\nu(\text{C}=\text{O})_{\text{CAK}}$ band intensities were used to estimate the concentrations of carbonyl species. The relative contribution of ester hydrolysis and oxidation could be investigated by assuming that any increase in the concentration of CAK species represents the sum of both oxidation and hydrolysis processes, while the decrease in ester concentration is caused by hydrolysis only.

Fig. 6 shows the concentration changes of CAK carbonyls (which are dominated by carboxylic acids) and esters as a function of aging time. In unpigmented LOp (Fig. 6a), there was a gradual increase in CAK carbonyls that was approximately mirrored by the consumption of esters, and the concentration changes showed a strong humidity dependence. This similar magnitude of ester consumption and acid formation and their sensitivity to humidity suggest that a large fraction of newly formed CAKs were the consequence of hydrolysis, rather than oxidation.

In contrast, R50 showed a far weaker humidity dependence for the formation of CAKs (Fig. 6b), and the increase of CAK concentration was more pronounced than the consumption of esters at all humidities. This indicates that carboxylic acid formation in R50 occurred through a combination of oxidation and hydrolysis, with the latter process becoming more significant with increasing humidity. A similar effect was observed for B50, (Fig. 6c), with particularly high concentrations of CAKs compared to ester consumption at 50%RH and 75%RH. The cause for this promoted oxidation in vine black oil paint is unknown, but it has been reported before by other researchers [25].

3.6. Effect of iron oxide pigment concentration on oxidation and ester hydrolysis

The surprisingly weak humidity dependence of the carbonyl region in red iron oxide paint indicated that reaction pathways that are less sensitive to water were more dominant during aging than for the other paint films we studied. An explanation for this observation can be that iron oxide promotes oxidation during curing and aging. To study this idea in more detail, paint films were prepared with 10, 20, 30, 40, 50 and 60 wt% hematite in LO and aged at 75%RH and 70 °C (Fig. 6d). The initial concentrations of CAK and esters after drying were rather different, and therefore absolute concentration profiles of CAK and esters are depicted.

As in previous experiments, during aging the concentrations of CAK and ester were increasing and decreasing, respectively. While there were differences in the concentrations of esters and CAK at short aging times in the series, suggesting that the iron oxide pigment concentration affects the rate/pathways of early-stage curing, all curves showed remarkably consistent carbonyl concentrations at longer aging times. This observation suggests that the position of the ester hydrolysis equilibrium in iron oxide paints does not depend on pigment concentration. It is interesting to note that, regardless of pigment concentration, the concentration of CAK in these iron oxide paints was markedly higher than in LOp films, while ester concentrations were comparable. This high CAK concentration suggests that hematite has a promoting effect on oxidation processes during oil paint curing and aging.

4. Discussion

The aim of this study was to investigate how humidity conditions and the pigment type influence the water-driven aging reactions in oil paint. Below, we discuss some limitations, context and implications of the current set of experiments.

The scheme for water-driven oil paint reactivity in Fig. 1 suggested that the ester hydrolysis equilibrium has a prominent role in oil paint degradation. We confirmed, for the first time, that hydrolysis indeed behaves like an equilibrium process in an iron oxide oil paint by monitoring ester and CAK concentrations under changing humidity conditions.

While earlier studies on oil paint aging have demonstrated increased rates of oxidation and hydrolysis under high humidity conditions, [1,24] the existence of an ester hydrolysis equilibrium was never suggested or observed. This is mostly due to the fact that investigating the character of chemical aging processes in detail requires a combination of reliable concentration estimates for chemical species, large numbers of samples and specific choices of (variable) aging conditions, which are usually not part of oil paint aging studies. Instead, we attempted to compare our findings to other polymer systems that undergo hydrolysis during aging, such as condensation polymers. The artificial aging, often referred to as accelerated weathering, of polyesters [42] and polyamides [43,44] has been extensively studied to assess their service lifetimes in specific applications, sometimes studying environmental humidity in particular. For instance, Pickett and Coyle investigated the dependence of the hydrolysis rate on internal water concentration for various condensation polymers during aging, revealing a second order relationship [45]. However, fundamental insight into the reversibility of the hydrolysis process in these polymers usually remains limited due to the application-driven nature of those type of studies in which mechanical testing (e.g. strength or flexibility) is used to evaluate material aging rather than chemical characterization techniques. For that reason, we were unable to relate the finding of an ester hydrolysis equilibrium in oil paint to other polymer aging studies.

Studying the effect of zinc oxide on an ester hydrolysis equilibrium (Fig. 1, part III), we observed a nearly complete consumption of both CAKs and esters during aging under harsh conditions, similar to previously reported experiments [20]. This reaction towards completion is in contrast with oil paints containing iron oxide, vine black or no pigment, where the concentration of carbonyl species seems to stabilize after a month or more of aging (Figs. 4 and 6).

Some researchers have suggested that the low concentration of esters in aged zinc white oil paints may be due to a catalytic effect of zinc oxide on ester hydrolysis. This idea is supported by various reports describing the use of zinc oxide as hydrolysis catalyst [46] and either zinc oxide or zinc carboxylates as ester condensation catalyst [47–50]. It may well be that zinc oxide, or the various zinc carboxylates that form quickly in zinc white paint, have a catalytic effect, but this is not enough to explain the differences between W67 and R50 paints in this study. Knowing that an hydrolysis equilibrium is reached in R50, if only catalysis by zinc oxide was happening in W67 that would just lead to a faster establishment of that equilibrium. Instead, the more dominant effect is the highly favorable complexation of zinc by carboxylate groups, which drives the hydrolysis reaction towards completion. This conclusion is even stronger with the knowledge that we observed no higher water concentrations with DVS in aged W67 compared to R50 which could have driven hydrolysis forward. It is worth noting that naturally aged zinc white oil paints often do retain a presence of esters, even after decades of aging at ambient conditions [51], which raises some questions about the representativeness of harsh aging conditions (see below).

Previous studies that used various chromatography methods and mass spectrometry to monitor aging oil paint related high humidity conditions to more extensive oxidation and hydrolysis [1,24,25]. While those methods necessarily involve some form of selective sampling

from an oil paint (e.g. through solvent extraction or pyrolysis), it is interesting to note that our spectroscopic method, which is less chemically specific but samples the paint as a whole, tells a very similar story. Beyond the effect of humidity on hydrolysis and oxidation reactions, the importance of oxidation pathways in the aging of iron oxide paints was also previously suggested based on GC–MS results [24]. We strengthened the idea of iron oxide as an oxidation catalyst by demonstrating that the rate of CAK formation was accelerated at high pigment concentrations while the final concentrations of CAKs were independent of iron oxide content.

For our reported findings, it is useful to discuss some methodological limitations. In the quantification of spectral data, several factors introduce uncertainties in the estimated concentrations of carbonyl species. For instance, the widths of the bands contributing to the carbonyl band envelope could not be deduced from the data, nor could they be estimated based on pure reference compounds, because the polymer matrix induces band shifts and broadening. However, they did need to be constrained in order to achieve converging fits, and therefore the band widths needed to be carefully, but empirically, estimated. Similarly, it was necessary to group carboxylic acids, aldehydes and ketones under a single contribution, even though carboxylic acids dominated this region, to avoid overfitting, and to introduce a non-interpretable absorption tail to avoid underfitting. Despite necessary approximations such as these, all trends in concentration data were supported by direct qualitative observations of the unprocessed spectra, and the concentration changes under varying humidity conditions were more substantial than the uncertainties introduced by the concentration calculations.

Within the humidity series (Fig. 4c), the obtained concentration ratios also showed considerable variation between duplicate samples. This is a phenomenon inherent to studying complex and to some degree uncontrollable materials such as aging oil paint, and stresses the importance of frequent sampling and measuring 3–4 duplicates per sample at minimum if any reliable quantitative conclusions are desired. Despite the spread of duplicate data, the differences between evolving $C_{\text{CAK}}/C_{\text{ester}}$ ratios at 75%RH and the lower humidity levels far exceeded this source of uncertainty, and we can safely conclude that the ester hydrolysis process was reversible in this experiment.

Finally, it is worth commenting on the use of high temperatures during oil paint aging. Increasing the temperature to accelerate aging is often necessary to induce a sufficient degree of change within a reasonable time [52]. However, high temperatures may lead to a faster evaporation of low molecular weight compounds [53] and a different equilibrium moisture content compared to ambient temperature aging. Moreover, increasing the temperature may bring the oil paint above its glass transition temperature and it can alter the relative rates of oxidation and hydrolysis processes. While the chemical mechanisms involved in aging are likely to be similar at 70 °C and at ambient conditions, the relationship between oxidation/hydrolysis processes in oil paint and temperature should be studied in more detail.

Having established that ester hydrolysis can reach equilibrium in an oil paint, it is useful to reflect on implications of this finding for the conservation of oil paintings. First of all, the equilibrium means that oil paint aging by hydrolysis is not always just a cumulative process. Especially short-term spikes in environmental humidity may lead to just temporary increases in ester breakage and carboxylic acid formation (process I in Fig. 1), which reverse once the normal humidity level is restored. While short-term RH spikes are associated with other types of risks like mechanical stress, the chemical impact may remain limited, providing opportunities for less-stringent indoor climate guidelines in museums. However, all this is only true for paints with pigments that do not form metal carboxylate complexes. In fact, our results suggest that any non-equilibrium process capable of disrupting the hydrolysis equilibrium will be particularly important as a driving force for chemical change in oil paint. For instance, evaporation of volatile aldehydes, acids and alcohols at elevated temperatures, and especially

complexation of metal ions with carboxylic acids (process III in Fig. 1), will have the effect of increasing the level of hydrolysis in oil paints. It is also worth stressing that our results clearly demonstrate that there is considerable variation in the response of oil paints to humidity depending on the pigment, with vine black paint showing extensive oxidation at high RH while iron oxide was much less sensitive to RH. This variability makes it rather challenging to draw general conclusions about the behavior of oil paint under a given set of environmental conditions.

With further refinements, the extraction of species concentrations from the carbonyl region of ATR-FTIR spectra is useful to determine oxidation, hydrolysis and metal carboxylate formation rates under a wider variety conditions and paint compositions. Those insights are useful for determining the temperature and humidity dependence of long-term chemical change of oil paints. In addition, our insights can ultimately be used to develop an empirical kinetic model for long-term aging of oil paints, or be integrated into existing mechanical [54] and moisture diffusion models for oil paints [55] to simulate the effect of humidity and temperature on the properties of oil paints. Such computational models can be used to access aging conditions/times that are challenging to study experimentally and aid future decisions on museum climate guidelines.

5. Conclusion

The aim of this study was to investigate the effects of humidity and pigmentation on oil paint aging by isolating simultaneous oxidation and hydrolysis processes with ATR-FTIR spectroscopy. In iron oxide oil paint, we demonstrated that the ester hydrolysis reaction reached a steady-state at long aging times and that it is reversible with changing humidity conditions. In contrast, the hydrolysis reaction reached completion in the presence of zinc oxide, which disrupts the hydrolysis equilibrium by forming zinc carboxylates with generated carboxylic acids. These results suggest that many types of oil paint may be rather insensitive to short-term humidity spikes. Secondly, the impact of constant humidity on the degree of oxidation and ester hydrolysis was examined. In general, a higher humidity led to more oxidation and hydrolysis products, although the relationship between humidity and oxidation and hydrolysis depends strongly on pigmentation. For example, oxidation plays a particularly strong role in aging of vine black paint, while aging of unpigmented linseed oil was dominated by hydrolysis.

Our ATR-FTIR method to calculate concentration estimates of carbonyl species is a valuable tool to investigate interlinked chemical processes in complex oil paint materials, though further refinements can be made to reduce uncertainties. It is now possible to quantify the effects of environmental conditions on oil paint aging in more detail and to distinguish different chemical aging pathways. This is particularly useful for the development of empirical or computational models for oil paint aging that may provide a foundation for conservation decisions on indoor climate conditions for paintings.

CRedit authorship contribution statement

Sander van Lith: Writing – original draft, Methodology, Investigation. **Katrien Keune:** Writing – review & editing, Supervision, Funding acquisition, Conceptualization. **Joen Hermans:** Writing – review & editing, Supervision, Methodology, Conceptualization.

Declaration of competing interest

The authors declare that they have no known competing financial interests or personal relationships that could have appeared to influence the work reported in this paper.

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Appendix A. Supplementary data

Supplementary material related to this article can be found online at <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.porgcoat.2025.109874>.

Data availability

Data will be made available on request.

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